

Influence of Access and Use of Non-English Collections on Research Activities of Postgraduate Students in Universities in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Going by Nigeria's colonial history, English language has been her lingua franca, hence the medium of communicating instructions in institutions of learning in the country. As a result of this, a great deal of library collections are written or presented in the English language despite having a significant population of users of non-English language collections. Consequently, this study intends to determine the influence of access and use of non-English collections on research activities of postgraduate students in universities in South-west, Nigeria. Three research objectives guided the study.

Method: The study adopted a descriptive survey research design with a population of 38,153 postgraduate students and a sample size of 380 respondents drawn from five selected universities offering postgraduate programmes in non-English specialties in South-West, Nigeria. Questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the data collected.

Findings/Results: The study revealed that access to archival materials, manuscripts, historical documents, and online multi-lingual databases is low. Furthermore, the use of archival materials, manuscripts, and historical documents written in indigenous and

foreign languages, rare or special indigenous collections, and online databases with multi-lingual collections to network and collaborate with scholars from different linguistic backgrounds is also low. This can be attributed to inaccessibility and unavailability.

Implications: The limited access and use of non-English collections hinder postgraduate students from fully exploring and leveraging linguistic diversity in their research. This underscores the need for infrastructural development and increased digital resources to bridge the gap in access and usage.

Conclusion: The findings highlight the need for improving access to non-English collections in university libraries to enhance research quality and foster academic collaboration among students and scholars from diverse linguistic backgrounds.

Recommendations: The study recommends that the universities studied should invest in better infrastructure and digital resources to enhance access to archival materials. They should implement strategies to increase awareness of non-English collections among postgraduate students, explore collaboration opportunities with scholars from diverse linguistic backgrounds, and ensure proper subscription and accessibility of electronic resources for postgraduate students.

Keyword: Access and use of non-English collections, research activities, postgraduate students, university libraries, South-West, Nigeria.

Introduction

Research activities of postgraduate students in university libraries have become iterative and more refined and organised as they become more knowledgeable in their respective fields of study, and their information use varies among disciplines and by programmes. Like other clientele of the university library, postgraduate students make use of both print and non-print (electronic) library materials that are available. Their research activities are influenced by convenience, speed and ease of access. These factors affect students' choice of libraries, library services and resources.

Universities are established to promote scholarly research, teaching, and learning in various fields of knowledge. Behind the mission and vision of the university, is the university library which is the academic resource hub serving the university community. Tom-George (2022) asserted that university libraries are indispensable nerve centres or hubs which serve as instruments for intellectual development. They are also social institutions to which faculty members and students turn to for accessing information. In

essence, no university in Nigeria and world over is established without a library. The practice is that a library is set up as soon as a university is established to enhance learning, teaching and research.

The goal of postgraduate programmes in universities is to achieve in-depth development of graduate students with the spirit of acquiring knowledge through training and research in an independent intellectual atmosphere and individual creativity with a strong sense of mutual cooperation (Owoeye & Owoeye, 2022). In the view of Bokoh *et al.* (2023), while all aspects of library services may seem important to librarians in their quest to support research, the case may not be the same with users, especially postgraduate students. The scholars asserted further that library use is the extent to which library facilities and resources are actually exploited by its clientele. This definition seems more acceptable considering the fact that patrons with the aid of technology now make use of library resources without stepping into the physical library space.

Going by colonial history, English language has been Nigeria's lingua franca, hence the medium of communicating instructions in institutions of learning in the country. As a result of this, a great deal of library collections are written or presented in the English language despite having significant population of users of non-English language collections in disciplines such as arts and humanities, natural sciences and social sciences. But in today's global society, proficiency in foreign languages is an important skill. According to Jaramillo *et al.* (2020), English has become the international lingua franca, making it indispensable for librarians and users to master the language in order to conduct research and communicate with their peers around the globe.

English is also the most widespread language in the world with about 1.5 billion people learning English as foreign language, which makes it the most widely studied foreign language in the world by far (Salomone & Salomone, 2022). This shows that English oriented collections are most predominant over the non-English collections in most libraries in Nigeria for users and particularly researchers. Without any doubt, there is a high tendency that some non-English collections could be more useful to some researchers.

Non-English collections or multilingual collections are library materials written in other language other than English language in print and non-print formats. The printed resources include periodicals (newspaper, journals and magazines), books, reference materials (encyclopedias, atlas, directories, dictionaries, maps), theses and dissertations among others. The non-printed resources include e-journals, e-books, e-theses, et cetera. These materials have to be acquired, processed, preserved and organised for use in the

same way as English collections. University libraries are meant to acquire materials that will match the needs of their parent institutions based on the programmes/disciplines of the institutions. Therefore, they have to acquire materials that are of use to users in non-English language disciplines. There are quite a number of non-English language disciplines and courses offered in our universities. These include African studies, Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa, French, Chinese, and Arabic languages.

Librarians as custodians of information must therefore consciously make every effort to ensure that various facets of non-English collections are available in the library and they get to the users at the shortest time possible. If university libraries are lacking in this role of collecting and preserving non-English collections, then the extent of the availability and use of these resources in their different subjects and formats may be low in the universities (Adejo, 2020). It is against this background that the researcher attempts to examine Information and Communication Technology proficiencies, access and use of non-English collections for research activities of postgraduate students in universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

In an ideal situation, university library collections that are available to faculty members, students and other users should not be restricted to collections solely in the English Language and printed formats such as books and journals. The actual situation is that university libraries place more priority on acquisition and management of English Language collections for the purpose of teaching, learning and research in their various institutions. Non-English collections are important information resources just like English Language collections. Preliminary investigation by the researcher revealed that disciplines in non-English do not have adequate information resources in university libraries resulting to students having difficulty in accessing non-English collections for research. It has equally been observed that despite the increment in the number of non-English programmes in the Nigerian universities, there has not been a significant development in their collections in the libraries thus, it is a matter of concern.

In view of the foregoing, it has been discovered that there is little or no empirical study that sufficiently investigated the influence of access and use of non-English collections as they affect research activities of postgraduate students in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria in recent time. Consequently, this study intends to determine the influence of access and use of non-English collections on research activities of postgraduate students in universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to establish the relationship between access and use of non-English collections for research activities of post-graduate students in universities in South-west, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the ease of access to non-English collection for research activities of postgraduate students in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria.
2. Determine the level of use of non-English collection for research activities of postgraduate students in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria.
3. Find out the extent of research activities of postgraduate students using non-English collections in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Research Activities of Postgraduate Students

Research activities of postgraduate students in university library becomes iterative and more refined and organised as they become more knowledgeable in their respective field of study, and their information use varies among disciplines and by programmes. Madu *et al.* (2019) opined that university libraries have a critical role to play in successful researches conducted by postgraduate students by providing a place for students and faculty members to do their research and advance their knowledge, provide collections of resources in helping these categories of users to find desired resources and reference services useful to their research activities.

The postgraduate students which are the focus of the present study are noted by Song and Song (2017) as students who are formally engaged in pursuing a course of study in a university with the aim of obtaining a postgraduate diploma, master's degree and Master/Doctor of Philosophy (M.Phil./Ph.D.). Postgraduate students form a significant group of researchers in a university and they rely on information (print and electronic) resources for their research (writing seminar papers, term papers, assignment, and other research activities).

Access to non-English Collections for Research Activities of Postgraduate Students

Access to library resources, and in this case, non-English collection, is the ease of locating and retrieving a piece of information from the storage medium. According to Usman *et al* (2019) readers tend to use information sources that require the least effort to access, so as to save time. The authors also defined information use as the practical and maximum use of library resources identified and acquired by a user for the purpose of solving a problem or achieving a set goal. Hence, university libraries are set up to provide access to available library resources and expert professional support to facilitate effective use of these resources. According to Adejo (2020), the mere acquisition of information resources by a library does not translate into accessibility. The author further explained that granting access to library's information resources requires a series of protocols which includes cataloguing, indexing, et cetera to ensure that users identify and locate the resources.

Use of non-English Collections for Research Activities of Postgraduate Students

Postgraduate students whose disciplines requires non-English, indigenous and foreign language collections have information needs just like other library users. In the library of today, with the emergence of internet, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) cum adoption of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in library routines, library collection now consists of both prints and electronic resources. In addition, the rapid growth of new technologies has changed the level of communication and as well changed the way and manner students search for information. When users of a library have adequate information on the resources that are available in the library, they are encouraged to use them as the need arises. According to Offor and Kamaluddeen (2017) Language is the chief means of communication among humans. In fact, in today's globalised world, the need for one to be bilingual or multilingual cannot be overemphasized particularly if one is to excel career wise.

Offor and Kamaluddeen (2017) further stated that several factors such as lack of foreign language proficiency among library personnel, lack of library services such as information accessing and dissemination in French, selection and ordering of books with French language titles as well cataloguing of these books hampers the access and usage of these non-English language collections by researchers in university libraries. However, the main challenges of information service delivery by libraries of in Nigeria as indicated by Hundo (2019) include lack of Internet facilities, lack of ICT devices and tools, epileptic power supply, unavailability and inaccessibility of non-English library and information resources. These factors resulted in low extent of usage of library resources.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research method and was conducted in universities in South-West, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised fifty-two thousand, three hundred and fifty-eight (38,153) postgraduate students. A sample size of three hundred and eighty (380) postgraduate students were drawn from three (3) federal and two (2) state-owned universities that offers postgraduate programmes in non-English specialties in South-West, Nigeria through the adoption of a purposive sampling technique and Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Table, while private universities were excluded from the sample because they do not have fully accredited postgraduate programmes in foreign and indigenous language disciplines. Furthermore, specialised universities were also excluded because they do not offer courses that require non-English collections.

The universities selected are Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State-120, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago Iwoye, Ogun State-20, Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State-10, University of *Ibadan*, Ibadan, Oyo State-140 and University of Lagos, Akoka Yaba, Lagos State-90. The proportion of the respective sample size was derived by dividing the population of a university by the population of the study (38,153) and multiplied by the sample size (380) that was derived from Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Table. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a five (5) point Likert scale. The initial draft of the questionnaire was given to two experts in test and measurement in the Department of Science Education, Federal University of Technology Minna, and a lecturer in the Department of Library and Information Science, Federal University of Technology Minna for face and content validation before adopting and administrating the research instrument for reliability test.

In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, a split-half statistical pre-test procedure was used. The research instrument was administered to thirty (30) respondents who did not take part in the final study. The result from the pre-test showed a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.89, 0.93 and 0.76 for the first, second and third research questions. A Cronbach's Alpha reliability of 0.86 was established using the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient Statistic. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, specifically frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Table 1: Sample Size of the Study

S/N	UNIVERSITIES	POPULATION	SAMPLE SIZE	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State	12,000	120	31.6
2	Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago Iwoye, Ogun State	1,861	20	5.3
3	Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State	246	10	2.6
4	University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State	15,000	140	36.8
5	University of Lagos, Lagos State	9,046	90	23.7
	Total	38,153	380	100

Data Analysis, Findings and Discussions
Response Rate

A total of three hundred and eighty (380) copies of the questionnaire were administered to postgraduate students in the five (5) universities where research was carried out in South-west, Nigeria and a total of two hundred and seventy-eight (278) copies of the questionnaire were returned and found usable with (73%) return rate. According to Luo (2020), if the sample size of a research is above one hundred (100) respondents or the population of the study is more homogenous, a response rate of 50% - 60% constitutes to fairly good representation. Thus, a response rate of 73% is deemed acceptable and reliable for the study.

Table 2: Response Rate

S/No	Universities	Total Administered	Total and Usable	Retrieved	Percentage (%)
1	Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State	120		81	67.5
2	Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago Iwoye, Ogun State	20		20	100
3	Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State	10		10	100
4	University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State	140		104	74.3
5	University of Lagos, Lagos State	90		63	70
	Total	380		278	73

Table 3: Descriptive statistics on ease of access to non-English collections on research activities of postgraduate students in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	N	D	SD	FX	X	StD
1	I have access to non-English materials such as Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa, Africana, French, Chinese and Arabic literature in the university library which is crucial for conducting thorough literature reviews.	57	141	53	26	1	1061	3.82	0.88
2	I have access to non-English collections which is essential for supporting my research needs in the university library	44	152	62	17	3	1051	3.78	0.82
3	I have access to non-English materials such as Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa, Africana, French, Chinese and Arabic textbooks and journals enriches my research by offering a comprehensive understanding of the research problem and diverse perspectives and insights.	54	133	66	19	6	1044	3.76	0.92
4	I have access to non-English materials such as Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa, Africana, French, Chinese and Arabic e-books and e-journals in the university library which influences my research work	39	177	41	18	3	1065	3.83	0.79
5	I have access to relevant non-English theses and dissertations in the university library which has a significant influence on my research.	45	138	72	19	3	1034	3.73	0.85
6	I have access to non-English collections in the university library which encourages me to develop language proficiency in other languages and analyze original texts other than English.	44	117	61	52	4	979	3.52	1.01
7	I have access to non-English collections in the university library thus allowing me to compare and contrast different cultural, linguistic, and historical contexts relevant to my research.	23	120	99	35	1	963	3.46	0.83
8	I have access to non-English collections such as archival materials, manuscripts, and historical documents, which are unique and invaluable primary sources, and also contribute to the richness of my research.	23	92	96	63	4	901	3.24	0.94
9	I have access to non-English collections in the university library to aid my research	14	103	98	57	6	896	3.22	0.9

	work on specific cultures, histories, or societies in order to develop a more culturally sensitive and contextualized approach.									
10	I have access to the library's online multi-lingual databases to facilitate networking and collaboration with scholars from different linguistic backgrounds, thereby opening up opportunities for joint research projects and cross-cultural exchange	6	26	79	128	39	666	2.4	0.92	
	Average Weighted Mean								3.45	

Key: SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, N= Neutral, D =Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed, \bar{X} =Mean, FX = Sum and StD = Standard Deviatio

Table 4: Level of use of non-English collections on research activities of postgraduate students in university libraries in south-west, Nigeria

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	N	D	SD	FX	X	StD
1	The use of indigenous non-English materials such as Yoruba, Igbo, and Hausa textbooks and journals in the university library significantly influenced my research.	56	67	51	60	44	865	3.11	1.37
2	The use of foreign non-English materials such as Africana collections, French, Chinese and Arabic textbooks, and journals in the university library has a significant influence on my research.	64	109	60	25	20	1006	3.62	1.15
3	I make adequate use of relevant indigenous and foreign non-English theses and dissertations in the university library to conduct a robust literature review and enrich my research.	43	168	45	21	1	1065	3.83	0.79
4	The use of indigenous non-English materials such as Yoruba, Igbo, and Hausa e-books and e-journals in the university library significantly influenced my research work.	2	29	37	124	86	571	2.05	0.96
5	The use of foreign non-English materials such as Africana, French, Chinese and Arabic e-books and e-journals in the university library has a significant influence on my research.	31	123	51	35	38	908	3.27	1.22
6	I make adequate use of indigenous and foreign non-English e-theses/e-dissertations in the university library relevant to my research.	34	126	88	25	5	993	3.57	0.88
7	I use archival materials, manuscripts, and historical documents written in indigenous and foreign languages, which are unique and invaluable primary sources that contribute to the richness of my research.	1	48	75	93	61	669	2.41	1.03
8	I use rare or special indigenous (Yoruba, Igbo and Hausa languages) collections in the university library that involve studying specific cultures, histories, or societies, which helps me develop a more culturally sensitive and contextualized approach to my research.	24	46	68	89	51	737	2.65	1.2
9	I consult online databases with multi-lingual collections to network and collaborate with scholars from different linguistic backgrounds, thus opening up opportunities for joint research and cross-cultural exchange	8	39	69	94	68	659	2.37	1.09
10	I also use non-English collections in the university library to develop language proficiency in other languages and analyze original texts other than English.	25	129	67	44	13	943	3.39	1.01
Average Weighted Mean								3.01	

Key: SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, N= Neutral, D =Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed, \bar{X} =Mean, FX = Sum and StD = Standard Deviation

Table 5: Descriptive statistics showing extent of research activities of postgraduate students using non-English collections in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria.

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	N	D	SD	FX	X	StD	Decision
1	I use non-English materials to conduct a comprehensive review of the existing literature to understand the current state of knowledge in my field of study.	81	131	47	13	6	1102	3.96	0.92	Agreed
2	I also use non-English materials to identify gaps in existing research and develop research questions and hypotheses.	53	148	59	9	9	1061	3.82	0.89	Agreed
3	The university library enabled me to develop my research proposal by outlining the objectives, methodology, and expected outcomes of the research using non-English materials.	73	111	68	21	5	1060	3.81	0.97	Agreed
4	I use non-English materials in the library to complete my assignments.	90	113	55	17	3	1104	3.97	0.93	Agreed
5	I extensively study non-English textbooks and journals in the university library to prepare for tests and examinations.	76	104	68	25	5	1055	3.79	1.00	Agreed
6	My research activities in the library also include learning how to navigate academic databases, library catalogs, and other scholarly repositories.	31	89	77	59	22	882	3.17	1.13	Disagreed
7	I retrieve information from various sources, including electronic databases, e-books, e-journals, and archival materials.	67	129	48	32	2	1061	3.82	0.95	Agreed
8	I use advanced search strategies such as my institutions' repository to find relevant and up-to-date scholarly resources related to my research work.	40	98	77	40	23	926	3.33	1.14	Disagreed
9	I use online databases that my university library currently subscribes to locate non-English information resources relevant to my research work.	24	79	93	70	12	867	3.12	1.02	Disagreed
10	I also use the university library to understand the preservation and handling of rare or fragile materials, archival materials, and special collections housed within the library.	20	79	93	45	41	826	2.97	1.15	Disagreed
Average Weighted Mean								3.58		

Key: SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, N= Neutral, D =Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed, \bar{X} =Mean, FX = Sum and StD = Standard Deviation

Discussion of the Findings

Based on the findings in Table 3, the low agreement concerning access to archival materials, manuscripts, historical documents and online multi-lingual databases can be attributed to various factors, including inadequate infrastructure, lack of digital resources, or a limited range of accessible databases. The fact that the mean score for this item is significantly lower than the average weighted mean highlights the need for improvement in this area. The findings align with that of Obiano *et al.* (2023) who revealed that the proportion of university libraries that adopt library database management systems is low and less encouraging and that academic libraries in federal universities make use of library database management systems more than academic libraries in state universities.

Findings in Table 4 revealed that the reason for low use of archival materials, manuscripts, and historical documents written in indigenous and foreign languages, rare or special indigenous collections, consult online databases with multi-lingual collections to network and collaborate with scholars from different linguistic backgrounds as outlined can be attributed to accessibility and availability. Furthermore, electronic resources, including e-books, e-journals, and e-these, might not be subscribed or might be inaccessible due to technical or subscription issues. In addition, postgraduate students may not be aware of the availability of specific titles or collections, limiting their use.

Table 5 revealed that the research activities of postgraduate students using non-English collections in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria are influenced by the type and currency of library collections within their reach. The respondents overwhelmingly agreed that their focal research activity in the university libraries studied is to complete assignments and conduct a comprehensive review of the existing literature to understand the current state of knowledge in their field of study. However, postgraduate students do not incorporate navigating academic databases, advanced use of search strategies and use of the university library to understand the preservation and handling of rare or fragile materials, archival materials, and special collections either due to inaccessibility or unavailability in the universities studied.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study revealed that there is low agreement among postgraduate students in universities in South-west Nigeria regarding access to archival materials and online multi-lingual databases due to inadequate infrastructure and limited resources. It can also be

concluded that the low usage of archival materials and historical documents is linked to accessibility issues and a lack of awareness among postgraduate students. In conclusion, the study revealed that the focal research activity of postgraduate students in the university libraries studied is to complete assignments and conduct a comprehensive review of the existing literature to understand the current state of knowledge in their field of study.

It is recommended that the universities studied should invest in better infrastructure and digital resources to enhance access to archival materials. University libraries in South-West, Nigeria should implement strategies to increase awareness of non-English collections among postgraduate students, explore collaboration opportunities with scholars from diverse linguistic backgrounds, work with academic departments to incorporate non-English collections into research and curriculum activities and finally, ensure proper subscription and accessibility of electronic resources for postgraduate students.

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